

SaaMS: The Synopses-as-a-MicroService Paradigm for Scalable Adaptive Streaming Analytics across the Cloud to Edge Continuum

Georgios Panagiotis Kalfakis^a, Nikos Giatrakos^{a,*}

^a*School of Electrical and Computer Engineering, Technical University of Crete, University Campus, Kounoupidiana, Chania, GR-73100, Greece*

Abstract

The use of data synopses in Big streaming Data analytics can offer 3 types of scalability: (i) horizontal scalability, for scaling with the volume and velocity of Big streaming Data, (ii) vertical scalability, for scaling with the number of processed streams, and (iii) federated scalability, i.e. reducing the communication cost for performing global analytics across a number of geo-distributed data centers or devices in IoT settings. Despite the aforementioned virtues of synopses, no state-of-the-art Big Data framework or IoT platform provides a native API for stream synopses supporting all three types of required scalability. In this work, we fill this gap by introducing a novel system and architectural paradigm, namely Synopses-as-a-MicroService (SaaMS), for both parallel and geo-distributed stream summarization at scale. SaaMS is developed on Apache Kafka and Kafka Streams and can provide all the required types of scalability together with (i) the ability to seamlessly perform adaptive resource allocation with zero downtime for the running analytics and (ii) the ability to run both across powerful computer clusters and Java-enabled IoT devices. Therefore, SaaMS is directly deployable from applications that either operate on powerful clouds or across the cloud to edge continuum.

Keywords: Data summarization, Data streams, Big data analytics, Cloud, Edge, Adaptivity

1. Introduction

Many modern applications from the financial, maritime, civil protection and other diverse domains base their business value on real-time, online Big Data analytics either at powerful data centers or over a number of, potentially geo-dispersed, devices across the cloud to edge continuum. In the financial domain, extreme scale stock streams, from various markets across the world, stream in investment companies' data centers. Global and continuous analytics over thousands, rapidly evolving stock streams need to be performed in real-time to timely pinpoint inter- or intra-market investment opportunities and risks [1]. In turn, such companies provide personalized portfolio management and investment services that span the cloud to fog to edge continuum to allow rapid trading on investors mobile devices. In the maritime domain, thousands of vessels across the globe are being monitored via satellite images, AIS receiver stations at regional coastal areas or unmanned vehicles swarming at sea to enable authorities to detect illegal activities or safety incidents [2] and act accordingly. In civil protection scenarios, drones, robots and sensors of various types operate in forest areas or along river banks. Such devices collect voluminous streams of relevant data in order to monitor environmental conditions and provide early warnings in case of forest fires or floods, among other events.

Over the years, there is an established consensus in the streaming data management community [3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10] that in

order to deal with the volume and velocity of such unbounded streams of data, data stream summaries including sketches [8, 9, 7, 10, 11], samples [6, 12, 12, 13], wavelets [14], histograms [15, 16] and dimensionality reduction techniques [17, 18, 19] can combine the potential to scale the computation by reducing the processing and memory load, while controllably sacrificing the accuracy of streaming analytics tasks, with predefined quality guarantees. Such summaries can provide analytics answers to a variety of commonly used, continuously executed queries that include, but are not limited to, distinct count, cardinality, frequency moment, correlation, set membership or quantile estimation [5].

To deliver Big streaming Data analytics at scale, stream synopses can provide three types of scalability:

Horizontal scalability: scaling the computation with the volume and velocity of data streams by reducing the processing and memory load via data summarization. In public or private cloud environments, this property can be combined with parallelization opportunities where each worker is assigned to process a disjoint subset of the incoming streams or a portion of an entire streaming dataset. In that, each worker operates independently on a portion of the incoming load and partial query results per worker can be combined (if needed) based on the mergeability property of many of such summaries [20]. In that, the virtues of both stream summarization and parallelization are exploited. Despite this fact, Big Data frameworks, like Apache Spark [21] or Flink [22], provide no Native API for data stream synopses [23]. Besides, these Big Data platforms can only aid in horizontal scalability at the cloud side as described above, while two additional types of scalability are required for real-

*Corresponding author

Email addresses: gkalfakis@tuc.gr (Georgios Panagiotis Kalfakis),
ngiatrakos@softnet.tuc.gr (Nikos Giatrakos)

time data stream processing at the cloud, and beyond the cloud side, as detailed below.

Vertical scalability: scaling the computation with the number of processed streams. For instance, in cross-stream correlation (stock-, vessel-, or sensor-streams in the aforementioned scenarios) computation, the complexity of the problem at hand is exponential to the number of processed streams. Therefore, mere parallelism cannot help by itself to reduce the processing load. On the contrary, stream summarization provides a scalable solution. In particular, sketch summaries [18, 24, 25] have been used for correlation/distance-aware hashing of streams to respective processing units. Based on the synopses, using the most significant DFT coefficients or compressed Locality Sensitive Hashing signatures as the hash key respectively, highly uncorrelated/dissimilar streams are hashed to be processed for pairwise comparisons at parallel processing units. Stream correlations are pruned for streams that do not end up nearby in the hashing space by exploiting such locality- and similarity-aware hashing schemes.

Federated scalability: This type of scalability involves scaling out the computation beyond single computer clusters or clouds to fully geo-distributed settings. Across the cloud to edge continuum, there exist a number of devices and intermediate nodes (sensors, robots, drones, Raspberry Pis) that do possess some processing capacity. Having these nodes naively relaying raw data depletes the available bandwidth and causes network latencies, thus hindering the delivery of real-time, continuous responses to running analytics [26, 27, 28]. By pushing the computation of stream summaries across the cloud to edge continuum, the processing capabilities of the entire network of devices can be exploited and the communication cost, as well as network latency, can be harnessed due to the use of synopses. Despite this fact, no IoT framework provides native support for stream synopses across the cloud to edge continuum [29].

The sole related work in the literature that provides a state-of-the-art parallel, stream summarization engine to support all the required types of scalability is SDEaaS [30, 31]. However, SDEaaS suffers from two inherent drawbacks: (i) it is not easily adaptable to changing stream summary maintenance conditions. This means that changing the parallelism of an SDEaaS service that runs at the cloud incurs significant downtime for scaling out or in (increasing or decreasing parallelism, respectively) upon workload changes and (ii) it cannot be deployed on devices across the cloud to edge continuum. The latter is both due to the fact that SDEaaS is built on a Big Data platform, not destined for resource constrained devices, and because of the downtime adaptation decisions incur for it. In particular, across the cloud to edge continuum, network devices may depart or connect at any given time due to sporadic connectivity or mobility characteristics. If synopses computation is assigned on such devices, every time they enter or leave the network an adaptation of the synopses computation assignment should be performed. Hence, continuous adaptation of the distribution of processing load among the devices is required in such cases. But the downtime that would be incurred by SDEaaS in order to adapt, would dominate the benefits of distributing the processing load among a dynamically changing population of devices.

In this work, we introduce a novel paradigm for parallel and geo-distributed stream summarization, SaaMS (Synopses-as-a-MicroService). SaaMS operates across the cloud to edge continuum and deals with all the aforementioned drawbacks. We describe an open-source [32] realization of SaaMS built on Apache Kafka [34] using the Kafka Streams API [35]. At the cloud side, SaaMS retains the ability to provide all the required types of scalability along with zero downtime adaptation to changing workloads. Across the cloud to edge continuum, contrary to prior art, SaaMS is directly deployable on Java-enabled devices incurring zero downtime adaptation upon changes in the populations of available devices which perform stream synopses computation. Therefore, SaaMS can simultaneously scale stream synopses computation at the cloud side and distribute synopses computation across network devices. In that, it fully exploits the lot of the processing capacity of the continuum.

Our experimental evaluation using hundreds of real stock and vessel data streams shows that SaaMS (i) scales faster than linearly with increasing stream volumes and velocities (horizontal scalability), (ii) maintains linear scaling trends upon increasing the number of processed streams from 10s to 100s (vertical scalability) and (iii) can save more than two orders of magnitude communication-wise across the cloud to edge continuum compared to naively using network devices at the edge as relay nodes (federated scalability). Compared to the state of the art SDEaaS approach which operates only at the cloud side, SaaMS exhibits an up to 3 times higher average throughput due to the fact that it diminishes downtime. Moreover, this especially happens in cases where the volume, velocity and the number of processed streams is significantly increased.

2. Related Work

From a research viewpoint, there is a large number of related works on data synopsis techniques. Please refer to [5, 40, 3] for comprehensive reviews on relevant issues. Such prominent techniques, cited in Table 2, are incorporated in SaaMS, which already includes a rich set of data summaries serving a wide variety of analytics tasks. What is more important is that SaaMS can incorporate any data summarization technique abiding by a simple, yet effective, software architecture (Section 4.3).

With respect to data summarization engines and libraries, Table 1 provides a comparison of SaaMS against prior art, regarding their scalability features, the level of the cloud to edge continuum where these scalability features are supported and their potential for adaptivity. Apache DataSketches [36] and Stream-lib [37] are software libraries of stochastic streaming algorithms and summarization techniques. These software libraries are detached from parallelization aspects. Therefore, they cannot provide horizontal, vertical or federated scalability at the cloud side. Moreover, they do not provide the primitives for IoT devices to coordinate and merge their partial synopses within the context of a unified synopses service. In other words, the application should manually install, program, synchronize and coordinate the IoT architecture from scratch.

Features →	Horizontal Scalability			Vertical Scalability			Federated Scalability			Zero-downtime Adaptivity
IoT Level →	@CLOUD	@FOG	@EDGE	@CLOUD	@FOG	@EDGE	@CLOUD	@FOG	@EDGE	ANY
Related Approach ↓										
DataSketch [36]	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
Stream-lib [37]	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
StreamApprox [38]	☐ (Stratified Sampling)	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
SnappyData [39]	☐ (Simple Aggregates)	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
Condor [23]	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
SDaaS [30, 31]	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗
SaaMS (this work)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Table 1: Scalability and Zero-downtime Adaptivity of Prior Art across the Cloud to Edge Continuum

SnappyData’s [39] stream processing is based on Spark and incorporates a limited set of synopsis serving simple SUM, COUNT and AVG queries. Similarly, StreamApprox [38] offers only sampling as a pipeline operator over Spark and Flink. Thus, these are deprived of vertical scalability features and federated scalability provisions at the cloud side. Besides their limited support for synopsis techniques (therefore the orange square in Table 1), SnappyData’s and StreamApprox operate on top of Big Data frameworks which are not deployable across the cloud to edge continuum.

The prominent work of Condor [23] elegantly optimizes the parallel computation of stream summaries at the cloud side, though neglecting vertical and federated scalability. SDEaaS [31, 30] covers all aspects of scalability at the cloud side only. Since Condor and SDEaaS run on top of Flink, they are restricted at the cloud level.

No related technique provides zero-downtime adaptivity at any level of the cloud to edge continuum. Indicatively, since SDEaaS and Condor are developed on Flink, they are running as Flink jobs at the cloud side. Our experience with adapting, even such simple stateless jobs says that it takes 10 to 15 seconds in case of adaptation (scaling in or out). This downtime intervals can considerably increase when state should be stored before and loaded after adaptation.

SaaMS also overcomes other limitations of SDEaaS including: (i) SDEaaS, by design, cannot use the native windowing operators of the DataStream API of Flink, while SaaMS incorporates the windowing operator of the Kafka Streams API, thus, offering additional parallelization strategies (Section 4.2), (ii) SaaMS allows to save and load saved synopsis to reuse summaries from past microservices, while SDEaaS always starts maintaining synopsis from scratch, (iii) Adding code of new synopsis on-the-fly, at SDEaaS runtime, is cumbersome due to Java ClassLoader usage, raising potential security issues in YARN-like clusters. On the contrary, adding code of new synopsis on-the-fly, at SaaMS runtime, just creates new MicroService instances without the need for ClassLoader usage.

3. Background

3.1. Apache Kafka

Apache Kafka [34, 35] constitutes the de-facto standard for stream ingestion in large scale, distributed, streaming applications [41, 42]. Kafka is a fast, scalable, durable, and fault-

tolerant publish-subscribe messaging system. A Kafka cluster is composed of a number of workers coordinated by a ZooKeeper. Workers are runtime instances ran on Virtual Machines (VMs) of a Kafka cluster undertaking the execution of data ingestion tasks.

Kafka receives and sends data using producers and consumers. A producer is a data source that initializes input by sending records to the Kafka log. The log typically consist of <key, value> pairs and, as its name suggests, it operates on an append only fashion.

The records that arrive at a Kafka cluster are categorized into topics based on the context the corresponding logs refer to. For instance, based on the running examples of Section 1, a Kafka topic may involve a group of stocks coming from the same market, in the financial domain scenario. The producer in this scenario generates and publishes financial market data, such as stockID (key) along with volume and prices per stock (value), or other relevant market events, into Kafka topics. In the maritime activity monitoring scenario, a Kafka topic may log vessel positions of a specific area of the oceans generating vesselID (key) and longitude, latitude (value) pairs. The actual context stored in the Kafka topics should be determined and defined by the application.

Automatically, each record of a topic is assigned a unique ‘offset’, which is a value that determines its position in the log. Kafka topics include one or more partitions for parallel processing purposes. A topic with multiple, non-overlapping partitions can be read (consumed) by different application instances, each reading and processing only a portion of the ingested data. Each partition has a leader instance held at one broker and replicas kept at the same or other brokers. Application instances should be equipped with Kafka consumers which read records using the offset as a pointer to identify where they previously stopped. A main characteristic of Kafka consumers is the organization into groups, allowing the distribution of partitions across the consumers of the same group. For instance, a topic with X partitions can have its records distributed among these partitions in a round robin fashion and a group of X or fewer consumers can operate on a separate subset of partitions each, reading and processing the records in parallel. In this case, a parallelization degree of X is achieved and the parallelism can increase in case a topic has more partitions. In general, the number of partitions of a Kafka topic sets an upper bound on the allowed processing parallelism by the applications built on top of Kafka. The above

Figure 1: Kafka Cluster Exemplary Organization. Coloring of topics and partitions expresses correspondence. For instance, grey partitions belong to the grey NASDAQ topic.

discussion is depicted in Figure 1.

Our SaaS framework communicates with the outside world, in the context of broader stream processing workflows, via Kafka topics which (i) consume streams and update maintained synopses, (ii) accept (consume) application/user queries and requests, and (iii) deliver (produce) the estimations provided by the maintained synopses as query answers in the output. Details follow in Section 4.1 and Section 5.1.

3.2. The Kafka Streams API

The Kafka Streams API of Kafka is a Java library for building real-time streaming microservices that can consume, process, and produce data from and to Kafka topics. It seamlessly integrates with Kafka, allowing stream processing applications to directly consume and produce messages to Kafka topics. This makes it easy to incorporate stream processing into existing Kafka-based architectures. Kafka Streams is a functional programming API that ensures fault tolerance exploiting Kafka metadata automatically created in the background and exactly-once semantics (each record is processed exactly once even in the face of failures).

Kafka Streams applications are Java applications composed of one or more microservices that can run on any Java-enabled device. The developer has just to produce a `.jar` file and deploy it to the desired devices (cluster VM or device, across the cloud to edge continuum). Separate devices can understand that they are part of the same application since they share the same `application.id`. The `application.id` is a unique identifier assigned to a Kafka Streams application, and it plays a crucial role in ensuring that instances of the same application coordinate and work together within the Kafka cluster.

A Kafka Streams application is composed of a number of processing and storing entities, besides producers and consumers described in Section 3.1. Below we summarize these entities focusing on their properties that justify the way they are positioned in the SaaS architecture later on in our discussion (Section 5):

- **KStream**: a high-level abstraction representing an immutable, ordered, and replayable sequence of stream records. Typically, each record is considered as a key-value pair. The term "KStream" is derived from "Keyed Stream".

- **KTable**: represents materialized views of changelog streams. KTables are immutable and maintain only the latest state of a microservice or application data, enabling efficient joining of streams or KTables. KTables are useful when the application needs to keep track of the current state of entities.
- **State Store**: provides mutable storage within a Kafka Streams application. State Stores can be used to maintain intermediate or aggregate state during stream processing. State stores allow updates, inserts, and deletions.
- **Serdes**: the term combines ser(ialization) and des(erialization) needed for transforming data (see stream transformations below) between microservices connected with Kafka topics and the internal representations used by the Kafka Streams application. The different workers (within a cluster) or various devices (across the cloud to edge continuum) need to communicate their transformed streams, the sender first has to serialize the data in a series of bytes so that they can travel via network channels, while the recipient has to deserialize bytes into meaningful streaming records.
- **Stream Transformations**: implement the actual data processing functionality of a number of microservices within Kafka Streams applications. Stream transformations typically are higher order functions taking as input or having a built-in anonymous function along with one or more Kafka Streams or KTables. Below we briefly mention the functionality of the major stream transformations used in the SaaS architecture:
 - `flatMap`: transforms each input record into zero or more output records by applying a one-to-many transformation.
 - `mapValues`: transforms the values of a stream without changing the keys.
 - `groupByKey`: groups records by their keys for further aggregation or processing.
 - `aggregate`: performs stateful aggregations on a (usually grouped) stream, maintaining results over time.
 - `windowedBy`: groups records into time-based windows for operations like counting or aggregating over specific time intervals.
 - `join`: combines records from a pair of sources based on their keys. For KStream-KStream joins, it matches records with the same key from two KStreams. For KStream-KTable joins, it combines KStream records with the latest record from a KTable based on matching keys. A `JoinWindows` parameter specifies time windows for temporal matching in both types of joins.
 - `transform`: allows the application of custom stateful transformations on each record in a KStream, providing flexibility for complex processing scenarios by maintaining and updating state across multiple records within a transformer.

Figure 2: Bloom Filter example on a current bitmap (synopsis state) with 2 queried elements (y, w) and set membership estimations.

3.3. Running Stream Synopses Examples

SaaMS supports a large set of synopses over streaming data (Table 2), but is extensible and customizable to any data summarization algorithm required by an application. In this section we are going to present two synopsis techniques, namely Bloom Filters [11] and AMS Sketches [43], which will be used as running examples in the following sections. Our focus will be on presenting (i) the way they reduce the processing and memory load and (ii) their update, estimation (querying) and synopses merging procedures. The reason for this, is that (i) and (ii) are at the core of the software technology in SaaMS design (Section 4) and the implementation of the SaaMS architectural framework (Section 5).

The **Bloom Filter** [11] is a lightweight and space-efficient probabilistic algorithm that can provide approximate estimations on set membership queries. The algorithm uses as its structure a bitmap of M bits with initial values set all to 0. L denotes the cardinality of the distinct stream elements (with $L \gg M$, therefore, the memory efficiency), and K are distinct hash functions used to map incoming stream elements to bitmap positions.

Update Procedure and Synopsis State: When a stream element x arrives, it is processed by a total of K hash functions. Each hash function is denoted as $h_i(x)$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, K$. The bit positions in the bit array are represented as:

$$h_1(x), h_2(x), \dots, h_K(x)$$

For each of these bit positions to which the hash functions points, the corresponding bit is set to 1. A bit already set to 1 by a previous stream element remains unchanged. The *state* of the synopsis at any given time is the bitmap itself with its set and unset bits in each position, as formed by updates received so far.

Estimation (Querying): Upon an application query, the algorithm estimates set membership of a queried element y in the set, by computing K hash functions on y . If all the bit positions, resulted from the hash functions, in the bit array are 1, y is in the set as illustrated in Figure 2. On the other hand, if for another element w there are 0 bits in any of these positions, then w is definitely not in the set (Figure 2).

The reason the algorithm does not respond with certainty is the limited size of the bit array compared to the cardinality of the original set of elements. As a result, different stream elements may hash to the same set of positions. The probability

Figure 3: AMS Sketch synopsis update and current state.

that all K positions are 1 for a queried element and this element did not appear in the stream so far is $FP = \left(1 - e^{-\frac{KL}{M}}\right)^K$.

To minimize the probability of a false positive (FP) result (the Bloom Filter erroneously replies that an element is in the set although it has not appeared in the stream so far), the number of hash functions should be set to:

$$K = \frac{M}{L} \ln 2$$

Merge Procedure: In case the stream is monitored in parallel by multiple workers or devices across the cloud to edge continuum, each instance of the Bloom Filter keeps a local state (bitmap) built on the subset of stream elements that have arrived locally. Local Bloom Filters can be merged into a global Bloom Filter, retaining the aforementioned properties of the synopsis, by performing a bitwise OR operation on locally constructed Bloom Filters. A Bloom filter requires $O(M)$ memory and $O(K)$ update, query and merge time complexity per parallel instance.

The key idea in **AMS Sketch** [43] is to represent a vector v , holding the frequencies of a large domain of streaming elements, using a much smaller sketch vector $sk(v)$. This vector is updated with the streaming tuples and provides probabilistic guarantees for the quality of the data approximation.

Update Procedure and Synopsis State: An AMS sketch is initialized as a matrix S with L rows and M columns (depth and buckets in Table 2), where $L = O(1/\epsilon^2)$, and $M = O(\log 1/\delta)$, with $\epsilon, 1 - \delta$ being the desired bounds on error and probabilistic confidence, correspondingly. L is the number of hash functions and M is the number of buckets. When an element e is encountered in the data stream, it is hashed L times using L independent hash functions. Each hash function h_i maps e to a bucket index j (where $1 \leq j \leq M$), and the count in the corresponding bucket for each row i is incremented (Figure 3). The AMS sketch defines the i -th sketch entry, $sk(v)[i]$ as the random variable $\sum_K v[K] \cdot g_i[K]$, where $\{g_i\}$ is a family of four-wise independent binary random variables uniformly distributed in $\{-1, +1\}$ (with mutually-independent families across different entries of the sketch). Using appropriate pseudo-random hash functions, each such family can be efficiently constructed on-line in logarithmic space. Note that, by construction, each entry of $sk(v)$ is essentially a randomized linear projection (i.e., an inner product) of the v vector (using the corresponding g family), that can be easily maintained (using a simple counter) over the input update stream. Similarly for element deletion – expiration.

Listing 1: Example of Streaming Tuple at SaaMS Data Topic.

```

1 {
2   "streamID": "Tesla Inc.",
3   "dataSetKey": "NASDAQ Stock Market",
4   "date": "01/02/2019",
5   "time": "00:00:01",
6   "price": 6.0654,
7   "volume": 1
8 }

```

The *state* of the sketch at any given time is the two-dimensional $L \times M$ array along with its count entries.

Estimation (Querying): An estimation on the cardinality of the “inner product” between two streams in the sketch-vector space is given by:

$$sk(v_1) \cdot sk(v_2) = \underbrace{\text{median}}_{j=1, \dots, M} \left\{ \frac{1}{L} \sum_{i=1}^L sk(v_1)[i, j] \cdot sk(v_2)[i, j] \right\}$$

For estimating the second frequency moment of a single stream we simply replace $sk(v_2)$ with $sk(v_1)$ in the formula above. **Merge Procedure:** In case the stream is monitored in parallel by multiple workers or devices across the cloud to edge continuum, each instance of the AMS keeps a local $L \times M$ matrix built on the subset of stream elements that have arrived locally. Local AMS Sketches can be merged into a global sketch, by entry-wise summations of the respective arrays. As mentioned above, AMS requires $O(M)$ memory and exhibits an $O(K)$ update, query and merge time complexity per parallel instance.

4. SaaMS Fundamentals

4.1. SaaMS API

SaaMS communicates to the outside world and broader application workflows, where it is deployed, via JSON formatted Kafka messages. JSON is used both to describe the schema of the incoming and outgoing data tuples, and as an API so that it can parse and accept instructions for (i) starting maintaining new synopses, (ii) querying existing synopses, (iii) updating existing synopses, (iv) saving the current state of a synopsis or loading a past synopsis and (v) deleting an existing synopsis. Because of this design choice, SaaMS can be part of any streaming processing workflow irrespectively of other platforms and tools that are deployed in the rest of the processing pipeline.

Listing 1 shows an example of a JSON formatted Kafka message which constitutes a streaming tuple destined to update an existing synopsis. We use the stock market scenario described in Section 1 as our running example:

- **streamID:** The name of the stream the tuple belongs to.
- **dataSetKey:** It represents a set of streams.
- **Field Name(s):** Represents the field(s) which may be used to build the synopsis on. In this example:

Listing 2: Example of New Synopses Maintenance Request.

```

1 {
2   "streamID": "Tesla Inc.",
3   "synopsisID": 1,
4   "dataSetKey": "NASDAQ Stock Market",
5   "param": ["CountMin", "volume", "Construct", 0.001, 0.99, 12345],
6   "noOfP": 5
7 }

```

Listing 3: CountMin [7] Query Example at SaaMS Request Topic.

```

1 {
2   "streamID" : "Tesla Inc.",
3   "synopsisID" : 1,
4   "dataSetKey" : "NASDAQ Stock Market",
5   "param" : [ 6, "volume", "Queryable", "Continuous" ]
6 }

```

- **date & time:** The timestamp at which the tuple (trade of `streamID` = "Tesla Inc." in the example) was captured.
- **price:** The current price at the specified date and time.
- **volume:** The quantity of a trade for the `streamID` = "Tesla Inc." at the specified date and time.

As another example, in the maritime scenario of Section 1, `streamID` would correspond to the identifier of a vessel, `dataSetKey` would correspond to a sea area, while application specific fields like `price` and `volume` would be replaced with timestamped vessel coordinates.

Listing 2 presents a JSON message with a request for starting maintaining a new synopses. In the example of Listing 2, the creation of a new synopsis is requested with specifications to create a CountMin synopsis on the `volume` attribute, along with necessary parameters (see Table 2) for that synopsis. In particular:

- **streamID:** As in Listing 1.
- **synopsisID:** Defines the synopsis type as a sequentially increasing integer for each of the synopses listed in Table 2. For instance, `synopsisID` = 1 corresponds to a CountMin sketch.
- **dataSetKey:** As in Listing 1.
- **param:** An array of parameters necessary to build the requested synopsis:

Listing 4: Request Message for Loading a Saved Synopsis.

```

1 {
2   "param" : [ "LOAD_REQUEST", PathToLoadSynopsis \ stored_CountMin.ser " ]
3 }

```

SynopsisID	Synopsis	Output Estimation	Input Parameters
1	CountMin [7]	Count, Frequency Estimation	ϵ (maximum error), δ probabilityOfExceeding ϵ , seed
2	HyperLogLog [9]	Cardinality, Distinct Count	Relative Standard Deviation (RSD)
3	BloomFilter [11]	Membership	Expected #Elements, False Positive Rate
4	DFT [18]	Correlation Estimation	Window Size, Slide Size, #coefficients
5	LossyCounting [13]	Count, Frequent Items	ϵ (maximum error)
6	StickySampling [13]	Count, Frequent Items	Support, ϵ (maximum error), δ Probab. of Exceeding ϵ
7	AMS [43]	L_2 Norm, Inner Product	Depth, Buckets
8	GKQuantiles [44]	Quantiles	ϵ (Maximum Error)
9	LSH [19, 45]	Correlation Estimation	Window Size, Compression Ratio, #Workers
10	WindowSketch Quantiles [46]	Quantiles	ϵ (Maximum Error), Window Size

Table 2: SaaMS Built-in Synopses, Input Parameters and Output Estimation. SaaMS remains extensible and customizable by plugging in new synopses.

- **Synopsis Type:** Specifies the type of the synopsis (e.g., CountMin) including those in Table 2 or custom synopses plugged in the SaaMS framework.
- **Field Name:** Represents the field used to build the synopsis on (e.g., "volume").
- **Request Status:** Describes the type of the request. In Listing 2 it receives the value of Construct to declare a request for start maintaining a new synopsis.
- **Synopsis Parameter(s):** Each synopsis has different parameters as in Table 2. For example, CountMin has ϵ , δ , and *seed*. These are instantiated in the example of Listing 2.
- **noOfP:** Defines the number of partitions in the synopsis data topics and the maximum parallelization degree of the synopsis microservice, to be further discussed in Section 5.1.

If a synopsis already exists, it is not duplicated. In case the *streamID* is empty, the synopsis will be maintained on all streams with the same *dataSetKey*. Moreover, the request for deleting a synopsis is similar to that of Listing 2, with *Delete* replacing the *Construct* keyword.

Listing 3 provides an example of a query on the previously created CountMin synopsis. The difference compared to Listing 2 is on the parameter array that is passed in the request. *param* is again an array of parameters, but this time includes the parameters that are necessary to query the involved synopsis:

- **Query Parameters:** Specifies the query parameters for the involved synopsis. In the example of Listing 3 we query the CountMin sketch (because *synopsisID* = 1) for estimating the frequency of trades with a volume of 6.
- **Field Name:** The queried field, *volume* in the example of Listing 3.
- **Request Status:** Describes the type of the request. In Listing 3 it receives the value of *Queryable* to declare a request for querying a synopsis.

- **Query Type:** Each query may either be a Continuous query, meaning that it is registered once and gets continuously executed until the synopsis is deleted, or Ad-hoc which involves one shot queries.

Finally, Listing 4 expresses a request for loading a previously stored synopsis, from a file of *.ser* type. This kind of request just uses the path from which the corresponding file should be loaded. Having issued a *Construct* request as in Listing 2, a *LOAD_REQUEST* follows in order to load a previously saved synopsis, instead of starting maintaining it from scratch. Having loaded a synopsis, it can get updated using tuples similar to the one in Listing 1, as well as it can get queried by receiving requests similar to the one in Listing 3. The request for saving the current state of a synopsis is similar, substituting *LOAD_REQUEST* with *SAVE_REQUEST*.

4.2. SaaMS Parallelization Schemes

SaaMS employs, and when needed combines, three parallelization schemes: (i) partition-based parallelization, (ii) key-based parallelization, and (iii) window-based parallelization.

Partition-based parallelization refers to the ability to process multiple partitions of a Kafka topic concurrently. Each partition is an ordered, immutable sequence of tuples, and consumers (workers at the cloud side or devices across the cloud to edge continuum) can read from multiple partitions simultaneously, allowing for parallel processing of data. This type of parallelism is used on synopses defined based on *dataSetKey* as detailed in Section 4.1. In this case, tuples of the same dataset are distributed among partitions (*noOfP* parameter in Listing 2).

Key-based parallelization, on the other hand, involves grouping records by their keys and processing records with the same key in parallel. This is particularly useful in SaaMS since we have data that may need to be partitioned based on a key, such as the *streamID* in our running example.

These two forms of parallelization are combined, depending on the synopsis type, in SaaMS by ensuring that tuples with the same key are sent to the same partition. By doing so, SaaMS leverages both partition-based parallelization (processing multiple partitions concurrently) and key-based parallelization (processing tuples with the same key in parallel within a partition).

Figure 4: SaaMS Library Software Technology (Package Structure).

In our running example, if we have a Kafka topic with stock trades from a market (the same `dataSetKey`) and we partition the topic based on `streamID`, tuples for the same stock will be sent to the same partition. This allows SaaMS to process data for different stocks in parallel across different partitions, while still processing tuples for the same stock in parallel within a partition, based on their keys.

Window-based parallelization, on the other hand, involves dividing data into fixed-size time intervals or windows and processing each window independently. This is particularly useful for handling streaming data where we want to perform operations, such as aggregation or computation, over a defined time window.

These forms of parallelization can be combined in SaaMS via the Kafka Streams library. In that, SaaMS allows the definition of windowed operations (Section 3.2), enabling the processing of data in parallel across different partitions within each time window. This boosts the ability of SaaMS for efficient and scalable processing of streaming data, taking advantage of both partition-based and window-based parallelization.

Such parallelization flexibility should not be taken for granted. It is based on the facilities provided by Kafka and Kafka Streams, but retaining these parallelization facilities, use and combine parallelization schemes is solely provided due to the unique Synopses-as-a-Microservice paradigm (Section 5.1) introduced by SaaMS. For instance, prior art [31, 30] is built on Flink, which supports window-based parallelization, but the SDEaaS framework built on Flink, fails to incorporate it natively and relies on manually programmed window configurations.

4.3. SaaMS Synopses Library and Software Technology

The SaaMS library is built using a simple, yet effective software technology that not only allows the incorporation of a large set of stream synopsis techniques (Table 2), but, importantly, remains extensible to new synopses and easily customizable to any application specific needs. This is in contrast to other large libraries listed in Table 1, which are extremely complex and hard to maintain and extend in the long run [42].

SaaMS avoids by design this complexity via two means. First, the design choice of using JSON formatted, schema-aware Kafka messages in its input/output. This alleviates the burden of incorporating schema details in the SaaMS software technology itself. This is in contrast to other approaches which define a separate class for any synopsis specific data type. As an example, DataSketches [36] defines a separate Java interface and classes for sketches of floats, sketches of doubles and so on. Second, the SaaMS library is built based on the observation that synopsis techniques rarely are complex algorithms themselves. Stream summarization algorithms fall into the category of clever, small and elegant probabilistic mechanisms that share the following fundamental operations (i) update a synopsis with a new tuple (add operation), (ii) provide an estimation upon getting queried (estimate operation), (iii) perform a merge operation in case a synopsis is maintained in a distributed setting, provided the synopsis itself possesses the mergeability property [20].

Figure 4 and Figure 5 provide a concise view of the SaaMS Synopses Library software technology. In the Synopses package (top of Figure 4) there is the abstract Synopsis class (middle of Figure 5). The member variables of the Synopsis class are the `synopsisID` and the `synopsisParameters` explained in Section 4.1. In addition to these, the `synopsisDetails`

Figure 5: SaaMS zooming in the Class Diagram.

member variable holds important information about the synopsis, including the key of the Construct Request and noOfP (Section 4.1).

The abstract `Synopsis` class (Figure 5) provides setters and getters for these member variables and requires for every subclass that inherits from it to implement the fundamental operations for each synopsis, as previously mentioned, i.e., the `add`, `estimate`, `merge` operations. Moreover, there are two additional methods, `size` and `serde`, for serialization and deserialization purposes (Section 3.2) upon operating in a distributed/parallel (within the cloud) or geo-distributed (across the cloud to edge continuum) setting.

Every specific synopsis technique, such as those cited in Table 2, inherits from the `Synopsis` abstract class and implements `add`, `estimate`, `merge`, `size` and `serde` as illustrated in Figure 5. It is important to note that all classes that have the `...Synopsis` suffix, arrange the details of the distributed/parallel maintenance and querying of the respective synopsis over SaaMS parallel architecture (Section 5.1).

Returning to Figure 4, around the `Synopses` package, there are separate packages for each specific synopsis technique. Figure 4 zooms in the `AMSSketch` package which includes 2 classes. The `AMSSketchSynopsis` which, as we already analyzed, in-

herits from the abstract class `Synopsis` in the `Synopses` package and takes care of the distributed/parallel synopsis over the SaaMS architecture. The second class is the `AMSSketch` class which is a simple `.java` file with the code of the respective (the `AMSSketch` in this example) synopsis. This class implements the logic of the synopsis, being totally deprived of parallel execution details. This is a design choice that boosts the extensibility of the SaaMS Library since any other existing library that implements a synopsis can be plugged in a separate package, as those around the `Synopses` one in Figure 4, and only a new class with the `...Synopsis` suffix, inheriting from `Synopsis`, should be created implementing `add`, `estimate`, `merge`, `size` and `serde`.

Speaking about the `serde` method, the SaaMS Library software technology follows a modular approach here as well, packing serdes in a separate package, `SynopsesSerdes` in Figure 4. The `SynopsesSerdes` package includes a separate sub-package for each specific synopsis technique and Figure 4 uses the `AMSSketch` sub-package to provide a zoomed in viewpoint and illustrate the contents of each such sub-package. In particular, the `AMSSketch` sub-package in the `SynopsesSerdes` package includes 3 classes. The `AMSSketchSerializer` and the `AMSSketchDeserializer` implement the actual serialization

and deserialization procedure, respectively, and include methods for configuring the (de-)serialization procedure and properly read/write bytes. The `AMSSketchSerde` class imports and uses `AMSSketchSerializer` and `AMSSketchDeserializer`.

The `AMSSketchSynopsis` class in the `AMSSketch` package (at the bottom left of Figure 4) uses the `AMSSketchSerde` of the `AMSSketch` sub-package of the `SynopsesSerdes` package (right-hand side of Figure 4) in the implementation of its `serde` operation. The corresponding dependencies are illustrated in Figure 4.

Summing up, to extend the SaaMS Synopsis Library, one needs to add a package for the new synopsis and include 2 classes in that new package. One that implements the pure synopsis algorithmic logic and one with the `...Synopsis` suffix which inherits from the `Synopsis` abstract class located in the `Synopses` package and manages parallel/distributed execution details. This `...Synopsis` suffixed class will be used every time we create a new synopsis microservice as will be detailed in the presentation of the SaaMS architecture (Section 5.1). Moreover, a new sub-package in the `SynopsesSerdes` package should be created along with classes implementing the serialization and deserialization procedures.

5. The SaaMS Framework

The SaaMS architectural framework is illustrated in Figure 6. Figure 6(a) shows a condensed view of the entire architecture. Each microservice and operator in the figure runs in multiple parallel instances. The data parallel view of a single synopsis microservice is illustrated in Figure 6(b) and the multi-synopses/ multi-microservice view in Figure 6(c). Section 5.1 presents the novel architecture of the SaaMS framework. Moreover, the details about SaaMS deployment across the cloud to edge continuum are discussed in Section 5.2. Finally, Section 5.3 discusses the way SaaMS achieves zero downtime adaptivity in case of scaling in (decreasing parallelism) or scaling out (increasing parallelism) at the cloud side, as well as when, across the cloud to edge continuum, Java-enabled devices occasionally connect or disconnect from the network.

5.1. SaaMS Architecture

Starting from the condensed view of the SaaMS architecture in Figure 6(a), SaaMS accepts new streaming tuples for updating maintained synopses (Listing 1) via the Kafka Data Topic. Furthermore, SaaMS accepts Construct (Listing 2), Delete, LOAD_REQUEST (Listing 4), SAVE_REQUEST requests via the Kafka Request Topic. The Request Topic is also used for Ad-hoc or Continuous queries (Listing 3). The exact details of the API used for the above operations were presented in Section 4.1. Both the Data Topic and the Request Topic are shown on the left-hand side of Figure 6(a) and they constitute the start of the green-colored and red-colored processing pipelines, respectively. The details of these pipelines will be discussed shortly, but for now we stress that by having streaming tuple updates (green pipeline) and requests (red pipeline) being ingested from separate topics, we ensure that SaaMS will

Figure 6: SaaMS Architecture under Different Viewpoints.

remain responsive to application requests even in edge cases where the green pipeline experiences extreme overload.

The implementation of SaaMS is composed of two categories of microservices shown in the middle of Figure 6(a). These categories involve (i) Router Microservices and (ii) Synopses Microservices. Each microservice for a specific synopsis Φ_i is termed as Synopsis Φ_i Microservice in Figure 6(a). A Router Microservice consumes tuples from the Data Topic, parses them and routes them to all the relevant Synopsis Microservices by producing messages for their input Synopsis Φ_i Data Topic. A Router Microservice also ingests and parses queries from the Request Topic and routes them to the Synopsis Φ_i Query Topic of the relevant Synopsis Φ_i Microservice. Let us elaborate on the details of each microservice.

5.1.1. The Router Microservice

The Router Microservice is the first microservice that should be initialized and act as a consumer of the Data Topic and the Request Topic. The parallelization degree of the Router Microservice is set equal to the number of partitions in the Data Topic and the Request Topic, but at any time during the SaaS operation we can create more, new Router Microservices or cease existing Router Microservice instances (discussed in Section 5.3).

As illustrated in Figure 6(a), the Router Microservice is composed of an Instance Lookuper KTable (middle of the Router Microservice in Figure 6(a)), Request Router stream transformations (bottom of the Router Microservice in Figure 6(a)) and DataRouter stream transformations (top of the Router Microservice in Figure 6(a)). The legend at the bottom of Figure 6(a) explains the shapes used to denote KTables, StateStores and stream transformations. All the stream transformation operators we mention in this section, have been introduced in Section 3.2.

Request Router: The Request Router consumes from the Request Topic and uses a FlatMap stream transformation in order to parse each incoming request (Listing 2). Having the Router Microservice up and running, when the Request Topic receives a Construct request, it follows part of the red pipeline. Each new synopsis that is created due to a Construct request is logged using its synopsisParameters, streamID, dataSetKey (Listing 2) and Synopsis Φ_i Data Topic as a key to the Instance Lookuper KTable. To check if a synopsis is already maintained, the Request Router applies a groupBy stream transformation on the Instance Lookuper KTable and a KStream-KTable Join on the aforementioned composite key to match the results of the groupBy with the details of the incoming Construct request¹. If the result of this join is empty for the provided key(s), the Request Router creates a Synopsis Φ_i Data Topic, a Synopsis Φ_i Query Topic and initiates a Synopsis Φ_i Microservice for the new, requested synopsis Φ_i . It also creates a Synopsis Φ_i Type Output Topic so that the synopsis can write there answers to posed queries. The Request Router logs the respective synopsis details, as described above, in a new KTable record in the Instance Lookuper. It also configures the partitions of the newly created topics and the parallelism of the new microservice based on the desired parallelization degree as declared in the noOfP parameter of the Construct request (Section 4.1). On the other hand, when the KStream-KTable Join is non-empty, no synopsis microservice is created, since this would result in unnecessary duplication of data and synopses.

Similarly, when a query reaches the Request Topic, the Request Router uses a FlatMap to parse the request, a group By and KStream-KTable Join to match the request with the name of the proper Synopsis Φ_i Query Topic of the existing synopsis that should be queried. A mapValues stream

transformation is used to forward the query (acts as a producer) to the proper Synopsis Φ_i Query Topic.

The rest of the requests (Delete, LOAD_REQUEST (Listing 4), SAVE_REQUEST) do not differ in the way they are processed, but the corresponding action of the Request Router does differ. In case of Delete, it stops the affected microservices and deletes the Synopsis Φ_i Data Topic and the Synopsis Φ_i Query Topic. LOAD_REQUEST (Listing 4), SAVE_REQUEST are forwarded to be handled by the Synopsis Φ_i Microservice since they store and load, respectively, the current state of a StateStore. The use of this StateStore will be discussed later on in this section.

Data Router: The Data Router stream transformations are applied on the green colored pipeline of Figure 6(a) for JSON formatted streaming tuples that are destined to update the maintained synopses. The Data Router consumes tuples from the Data Topic. It uses a FlatMap transformation to parse the respective JSON (Listing 1), a groupBy and KStream-KTable Join to match the streaming tuple with the name of the proper Synopsis Φ_i Data Topic of the existing synopsis, and forwards the tuple (acts as a producer) to the proper Synopsis Φ_i Data Topic.

5.1.2. Synopsis Microservices

In Figure 6(a), each Synopsis Φ_i Microservice includes updateSynopsis, mergeSynopsis and queryAnswer stream transformations, as well as a SynopsisStateStore and an AggregationStateStore. We will set out our description from updateSynopsis.

updateSynopsis: The updateSynopsis is a transform operator (Section 3.2) which consumes from Synopsis Φ_i Data Topic and executes the add method of the corresponding synopsis as presented in the class diagram of Figure 5. In that, it updates the status of the maintained synopsis, for instance, if a BloomFilter is maintained, it turns some of the bits of the respective bitmap to 1 and stores the state of the synopsis (Section 3.3, Figure 2) in the SynopsisStateStore.

SynopsisStateStore: The SynopsisStateStore maintains a local copy of the current state of the synopsis in each parallel instance, worker at the cloud side or device in the cloud to edge continuum. For instance, in case of a BloomFilter, the SynopsisStateStore stores the current state of its bitmap (Figure 2).

mergeSynopsis: The mergeSynopsis is a transform operator which consumes from Synopsis Φ_i Query Topic and executes the merge method of the corresponding synopsis as presented in the class diagram of Figure 5. mergeSynopsis of each parallel/distributed synopsis instance is executed, reading the current state of the synopsis from the local SynopsisStateStore and passing it on to the (global) AggregateStateStore before applying the respective merge method (Section 3.3). In case a synopsis is not mergeable, AggregateStateStore will have a single record from the single SynopsisStateStore. Finally, mergeSynopsis computes the merged state of the synopsis and gives this representation to the queryAnswer stream transformations. For instance, in case of a parallel/distributed Bloom Filter, local bitmaps are merged by applying a bitwise

¹Note that the groupBy here is necessary since a Construct request may instruct the creation of multiple synopsis in a single request

OR operation on the local versions of Bloom Filters per worker/device and the resulted, final bitmap is the global state of the synopsis that is conveyed to `queryAnswer`.

queryAnswer: The `queryAnswer` executes the `estimate` function (once for Ad-hoc queries and continuously for Continuous queries, see Section 4.1) from the corresponding synopsis as presented in the class diagram of Figure 5. It additionally uses a `mapValues` transformation to produce a tuple for the `Synopsis Φ_i Type Output Topic`, where the query response is recorded for the rest of the application pipelines to consume.

5.1.3. Data Parallel View

Figure 6(b) illustrates how SaaMS operates in multiple parallel instances. To keep the figure readable, we illustrate parallelization for a single maintained synopsis. Each one of the `Data Topic` and `Request Topic` include n partitions. The number of partitions in these topics poses an upper bound n on the parallelism of the `Router Microservice`. That is, if the `Router Microservice` includes fewer than n parallel instances, some instances will have to process more than one partitions. If the `Router Microservice` includes more than n parallel instances, some of these instances will remain idle.

On the other hand, the `Synopsis Φ_i Data Topic` and the `Synopsis Φ_i Query Topic` run under k partitions which also poses an upper bound k on the parallelization degree (number of parallel instances, `noOfP` parameter in Listing 2) of the `Synopsis Φ_i Microservice`. Practically, there is no restriction in the SaaMS implementation with respect to which, between n and k , is greater. Depending on the load (see Section 5.3) the concept is that we always provision n and k so that SaaMS applications can then dynamically adjust the number of parallel instances of `Router Microservice` and `Synopsis Φ_i Query Topic` within $[1, n]$ and $[1, k]$ respectively. Typically, because the `Router Microservice` handles the lot of incoming streams via the `Data Topic`, $n > k$.

Based on our discussion in Section 4.2, the `Router Microservice` applies partition- and key-based parallelization, while the `Synopsis Φ_i Microservice` applies, in addition, window-based parallelization in cases of windowed synopses (Table 2).

5.1.4. Multi-synopsis View

Figure 6(c) presents the parallel maintenance of multiple synopses. Each of these synopses runs in multiple parallel instances as shown in Figure 6(b), but Figure 6(c) stresses the facts that (i) in addition to having a single synopsis in multiple parallel instances, SaaMS achieves scalability via parallel maintenance of multiple such synopses and (ii) we can have multiple synopses of the same type (e.g. `CountMin` in Figure 6(c)) defined on different fields (included in the `param` part of the JSON request in Listing 2). Furthermore, Figure 6(c) shows the fact that the `Synopsis Φ_i Type Output Topic` is the same for synopses of the same type. This is because synopses of the same type (`CountMin`, `HLL`, `Bloom Filter` in the figure) provide their query responses using the same schema in the outputted tuples.

5.2. SaaMS across the Cloud to Edge Continuum

As discussed in Section 3.2, a Kafka Streams program has an `application.id`. Besides the `application.id` of SaaMS, we use `microservice.ids`. The `microservice.id` of the `Router Microservice` is set to `router-microservice`. Every synopsis created upon request (Section 4.1, Section 5.1) has a different `microservice.id` which is automatically set to `synopsiSeqNoMicroservice.seqNo` stands for a sequential integer attributed by the `Router Microservice` when it creates the corresponding `Synopsis Φ_i Microservice`. These `microservice.ids` enable multiple parallel instances of the same `microservice` act as a consumer group.

Given a Kafka Cluster along with its brokers (Figure 3.1), SaaMS, with `microservice.ids` configured and dynamically created as previously described, is simply submitted as a `.jar` to each among multiple VMs at the cloud side and other Java-enabled devices across the cloud to edge continuum. The rest is automatically configured by Kafka and Kafka Streams, which justifies and supports our choice of implementing SaaMS using the `microservice` paradigm. More precisely, Kafka Streams leverages Kafka's consumer group mechanism (Section 3.1) for parallelizing the processing. Let us detail how this approach works:

- **Consumer Groups:** Kafka Streams assigns each instance of SaaMS's microservices running on different VMs/devices to consumer groups. This ensures that each VM/device acts as a consumer within the same group for the topics of each microservice, and Kafka partitions all the relevant topics' data (Section 5.1) across these instances.
- **Partition Assignment:** Kafka assigns different partitions of topics to different instances of SaaMS within that same consumer group. Each instance processes the messages in the partitions it is assigned, allowing for parallel processing.
- **Parallel Processing:** With each instance of SaaMS running on separate VMs/devices and processing different partitions of data, parallel processing is achieved. Each instance independently consumes, processes, and produces data, contributing to the overall throughput (number of tuples being processed per time unit) of the Kafka Streams application.

Figure 7 illustrates an exemplary deployment of the data parallel view of SaaMS as presented in Figure 6(b) but, this time, over a distributed setting composed of: (i) a Kafka Cluster (for better illustration, respective topics and partitions are placed on the left and the right of the figure) with $n = k = 6$ partitions for all the involved topics, (ii) a cloud side composed of a computer cluster of 3 VMs, (iii) 3 Raspberry Pi devices and (iv) 2 drones. It can be observed that the various instances of the `Router Microservice` and the `Synopsis Φ_i Microservice` are distributed across the available devices. Partition assignment according to consumer groups is denoted by

Figure 7: SaaS Deployment View across the Cloud to Edge Continuum. The names of the partitions that are assigned to each instance of a microservice appears beside their name. Green colored text corresponds to partitions of the Data Topics, while red colored text in the name of the partitions corresponds to Request and Query Topics.

the name of the partitions that are handled by the various VMs/devices, next to the name of the microservice instances that are assigned to them.

Notably, Kafka Streams internally optimizes the processing topology of SaaS to ensure efficient parallelization while minimizing data shuffling and network overhead. In particular:

- **Task Assignment:** Kafka Streams breaks down the processing tasks of SaaS into smaller sub-tasks known as stream tasks. Each stream task processes data from one or more input partitions of Kafka topics. These tasks are then assigned to different instances of SaaS running on the available VMs/devices.
- **Task Distribution:** Kafka Streams distributes these stream tasks across the instances of SaaS in a balanced manner. It, by default, aims to evenly distribute the workload among the available instances, ensuring optimal resource utilization and parallelism.
- **Stateful Operations:** For stateful operations like aggregations or joins, Kafka Streams also manages the distribution of state stores across instances. It ensures that each instance has access to the necessary state data for processing its assigned tasks efficiently.

- **Data Shuffling Optimization:** Kafka Streams minimizes the need for data shuffling across SaaS tasks, which involves transferring data between instances. It achieves this by co-locating stream tasks with their required input partitions whenever possible. By processing data locally, Kafka Streams reduces the amount of data that needs to be transferred over the network, boosting federated scalability.
- **Fault Tolerance:** Kafka Streams maintains fault tolerance by replicating state stores and redistributing stream tasks in case of instance failures. This ensures that processing continues seamlessly even in the event of VM/device failures or device disconnections from the rest of the network.

5.3. SaaS Zero Downtime Adaptivity

Another important feature which justifies and supports our focus on the Synopses-as-a-Microservice paradigm is the ability to automatically adapt to workload and network changes with virtually zero downtime. This is an important and desired feature because, across the cloud to edge continuum, network devices often lose connectivity due to the, potentially harsh, environment they operate and due to potential mobility character-

Figure 8: SaaS Zero Downtime Adaptivity. The blue drone disconnects from the network and the partitions that were previously assigned to it, are automatically re-assigned to the Raspberry Pi at the bottom right of the figure.

istics of the various devices. Therefore, when new network devices connect, SaaS has the potential of using more microservice instances (scales out). When devices disconnect, SaaS forcefully loses instances (scales in). Figure 8 shows an example where the blue drone of Figure 7 loses connectivity. The blue drone is initially hosting Synopsis Φ_i Microservice Instance 5 and is responsible for Synopsis Φ_i Data Topic Partition 5 and Synopsis Φ_i Query Topic Partition 5. Upon its departure, these partitions are seamlessly re-assigned, for the sake of the example, to the Raspberry Pi at the bottom right of Figure 8.

This automatic reassignment is handled by Kafka’s consumer group protocol together with Kafka Streams’ task rebalance logic. Out of the box, that mechanism operates per consumer group, i.e., per application.id. SaaS contributes by adding the Router Microservice, which wraps every synopsis in its own Kafka Streams application (see Section 5.2, synopsisSeqNoMicroservice). Because each synopsis now forms an independent consumer group, it can fully exploit Kafka’s native rebalancing whenever additional processing instances are started or existing ones are stopped across the cloud to edge continuum, without manual coordination, given the involved

synopses maximum allowed parallelism (noOfP, Section 4.1). If an application needs to shut down, adapt and then restart every time a device joins or departs from the network, this would have a devastating effect on its performance. This is because, during downtime, incoming streams are not processed and, thus, all the involved topics (Figure 6) would flood with unprocessed tuples.

Kafka makes this avoidable by persisting every record and letting new consumers resume exactly where the departed ones stopped, while Kafka Streams transparently replays data during a rebalance. Nonetheless, Kafka natively does that only for the raw streams. SaaS excels this built-in behavior by maintaining synopsis (instead of raw data) state in the Instance Lookuper as a KTable and the SynopsisStateStore as a state store. In that, state management and replay costs stay proportional to the, much smaller, synopsis size instead of the raw stream volume.

Additionally, also at the cloud side, one may need to reduce (scale in) or increase (scale out) parallelism by decreasing (resp. increasing) the number of utilized VMs and/or the threads within each VM, so that system performance metrics (e.g. throughput) abide by quality of service criteria. In the later

case, the exact mechanism with which scale in and scale out is determined is orthogonal to the general operation of SaaMS. Irrespective of the employed decision making procedure, SaaMS will adapt with virtually zero downtime avoiding zero throughput during adaptation decisions. As explained in Section 6, SaaMS provides a JMX-based statistics monitoring hook that exports device-level metrics to aid any given autoscaling policy.

In order to achieve zero downtime adaptivity, SaaMS exploits the built in mechanisms provided by the microservice architecture of Kafka and Kafka Streams. This is a great difference compared to other Big Data platforms such as Apache Spark or Flink. More precisely, with respect to scaling in, Kafka Streams automates the following procedures:

- **Rebalancing Process:** When scaling in, SaaMS lets Kafka Streams to automatically trigger a rebalance operation in order to redistribute the processing workload among the remaining instances. This involves gracefully removing instances from the consumer group and reallocating their processing tasks and partitions to the remaining instances.
- **Task Redistribution:** SaaMS, via Kafka Streams default behavior, redistributes the stream processing tasks among the remaining instances to ensure even workload distribution. Each stream task processes data from one or more input partitions of Kafka topics.
- **State Management:** During scaling in, SaaMS exploits Kafka Streams native mechanisms to ensure that state stores and KTables associated with the scaled-in instances are properly managed. State data may be migrated to other instances, ensuring that stateful operations maintain data integrity and processing continuity.
- **Graceful Shutdown:** Scaled-in instances of SaaMS gracefully shut down their processing tasks, ensuring that all pending data is processed before exiting the consumer group. This prevents data loss and ensures that no processing interruptions occur during the scaling process.

Upon scaling in with plain Kafka Streams, all topologies that share the same `application.id` belong to a single consumer group. Using only the native Kafka behavior, if one member node (device or VM) is removed during scale in, rebalancing, task redistribution and state management should be handled for the entire application, even for synopses that never ran on the departed node. SaaMS better isolates and limits this failure effect by assigning each synopsis its own `microservice.id` (see Section 5.2) through the `Router Microservice`, which means each synopsis has an independent consumer group. When a device leaves, state management procedures, rebalance and redistribution is restricted to the consumer groups of synopses that actually had tasks on that device. Synopses hosted on other nodes continue processing without interruption or overhead. Thus SaaMS localizes scale in only to the truly affected synopses, instances and nodes of the continuum, minimizing

the effect of the aforementioned scale in procedures, compared to the default Kafka Streams behavior.

For scaling out, SaaMS again leverages the default functionality provided by Kafka Streams which automates the following procedures:

- **Dynamic Rebalancing:** When scaling out, new instances of SaaMS join the consumer group, with Kafka Streams automatically triggering a rebalance to redistribute processing tasks and partitions among all instances. This dynamic rebalancing ensures that the new instances participate in processing immediately upon joining the group.
- **Task Assignment:** SaaMS, via Kafka Streams, assigns stream processing tasks to the new instances, ensuring that the workload is evenly distributed across all available resources. Each new instance receives a subset of the processing tasks based on the partition assignment strategy.
- **State Replication:** Stateful operations, such as aggregations or joins, state stores, KTables of SaaMS are, by default, replicated by Kafka Streams to the new instances as needed. This ensures that each instance has access to the required state data for processing its assigned tasks.
- **Fault Tolerance:** SaaMS maintains fault tolerance during scaling out by having Kafka and Kafka Streams replicating state stores, KTables and redistributing processing tasks in the event of instance failures or restarts. This ensures that processing continues seamlessly even in the face of transient failures or infrastructure changes.

During scaling out, the SaaMS architecture (Section 5.1) adds an orchestration layer to the default Kafka behavior. The `Router Microservice` allows to spawn a new Kafka Streams instance only for those synopses that still have spare parallelism under their `noOfP` limit (see Section 4.1). The `Router` derives the unique `microservice.ids` of those synopses, the correct topic sets, and the new instance immediately joins the proper consumer groups, receiving the corresponding partitions, tasks, and states. Without these SaaMS conventions, under the default Kafka functionality, each synopsis would have to be launched by an operator as a separate process with the right configuration. Task assignment, state replication, and rebalancing across concurrently maintained synopses would therefore require manual coordination every time additional devices become available.

Achieving Zero Downtime via the Kafka Streams native mechanisms:

- **Continuous Processing:** Throughout the scaling process, SaaMS use the Kafka Streams functionality to ensure continuous data processing without any downtime or interruptions. Stream processing tasks are reassigned and executed on available instances in a seamless manner, ensuring that data is processed without delay.
- **Transparent Rebalancing:** SaaMS over Kafka Streams handles the rebalancing process transparently, abstracting the complexity of instance addition or removal from

the application logic. Consumers interacting with SaaMS experience minimal to no disruption, as Kafka manages the rebalancing process internally.

- **Atomicity and Consistency:** Kafka ensures atomicity and consistency during rebalancing operations to prevent data inconsistencies or processing anomalies. Stateful operations maintain data integrity, and Kafka’s consumer group coordination ensures that all instances agree on the partition assignments and processing responsibilities.

In all, SaaMS turns Kafka’s generic rebalance machinery into an application-aware, continuum-wide control plane. Each synopsis is shipped as a lightweight microservice with its own consumer group, so failures or scale in events trigger partition movement, state migration, and task activation *only* for the synopses that were actually running on the affected node(s). SaaMS further orchestrates automatic scale out procedures by launching new instances whenever spare capacity appears when new nodes join, letting synopses microservices that have not exceeded their `noOfP` parallelism cap exploit the newly introduced resources. Because the state that moves is a compact synopsis (KTables / state stores) instead of raw streams, replay and recovery overhead remain minimal, while JMX-based feeds make any autoscaling policies orthogonal to SaaMS. The result is virtually zero downtime, minimal recovery latency, and enhanced elasticity capabilities that plain Kafka Streams cannot deliver on its own for concurrently running synopses without continuous manual intervention.

6. Experimental Evaluation

For repeatability purposes, we provide a detailed description of our experimental setup.

SaaMS Open Source Repository: SaaMS code is available as open-source software [32], along with detailed installation instructions for both bare-metal setups (used in this experimental evaluation) as well as via Docker containers. SaaMS has been developed using Kafka and Kafka Streams 3.3.1. It has been tested with Zookeeper 3.9.0, Java 19, and Maven 3.6.3. Backward compatibility has also been verified with versions of Kafka down to 2.8.1. The `Scripts` folder of the repository provides the necessary scripts for starting the Kafka brokers and a Zookeeper Server. The `RequestExamples` folder includes the exemplary syntax for all possible requests (Section 4.1) across supported synopses, including those used in the experiments presented below.

Statistics Collector: In our experiments, we monitor relevant performance metrics (throughput and communication cost) using JMX technology². The JMX API is a standard API for monitoring and managing resources, Kafka Streams applications, devices, services, and Java Virtual Machines themselves. JMX provides tools for local and remote monitoring, as well

as capabilities for collecting and exposing application performance statistics in real-time. Our lightweight statistics collector is available in the `metrics` directory of SaaMS code repo. It connects to every Kafka Streams JVM and polls it over JMX, so as to monitor both processing speed and application level communication cost, anywhere from the cloud down to edge devices. Inside each SaaMS task running on a device, a `ByteCountingSensor` registers custom byte counters with the `StreamsMetrics` registry, which are then exposed as JMX MBeans. A command line interface (`MetricsUserInterface`) receives a comma separated list of JMX service URLs, one per node in the cloud-to-edge continuum, and establishes two collectors: (i) the `ThroughputJMXMetrics` collector aggregates the thread level throughput from every URL/device periodically (the period is expressed as a configurable number of seconds) and appends a timestamped block to a report, (ii) the `CommunicationCostJMXMetrics` collector snapshots the two custom byte counters once and prints the network wide totals to `stdout`. Because the statistics collector scrapes any JMX endpoint, it works across heterogeneous nodes (cloud VMs, fog gateways, Raspberry Pis) so long as we expose the right port and enable JMX.

Hardware Setup: For our experimental set up, we have a network composed of a cloud and a network side with the following characteristics: *Cloud side*, running Ubuntu 22.04.3 LTS server, equipped with (a) Two Intel Xeon Silver 4310 processors with 12 cores and 24 threads each, (b) Four 64GB RAMs RDIMM 3200MT/s each, (c) One ROM 960GB SSD vSAS with read-intensive 12Gbps. *Network side* with 5 VMs running Raspberry Pi OS (Debian GNU/Linux 11) each with a hardware configuration of (a) One CPU, (b) 16GB RAM, (c) 30GB ROM.

Datasets: We use two real datasets from the stock market [47, 48] and the maritime domain [2, 50].

The full stock market data spans from 1 January 2019 to 31 December 2019, covering more than 500 tradeable instruments: forty-nine Forex pairs, nine spot-crypto pairs, twenty ICE & CME futures contracts (energy, metals, rates, and index futures), eleven synthetic equity index contracts, four proprietary gaming tokens, the rest being cash equities partitioned by market (200+ US, 130+ UK, 80+ FR, 70+ DE, 30+ ES, 10+CH, and 10+ NL). Each trading day is in a `quotes/` directory of tick-by-tick files and a companion `history/` directory of one minute OHLCV (Open, High, Low, Close, and Volume) aggregates; the tick files contain four comma separated fields: Date, Time, Price (native currency), and Volume. A single day contributes on average 8.4×10^6 ticks ($\sigma = 0.9 \times 10^6$), of which Forex accounts for 39%, US equities 29%, futures 13%, index synthetics 7%, European equities 11%, and the remaining asset classes < 1%. Scaling the daily figure to the 252 trading sessions of 2019 yields roughly 3.1×10^9 quotes and trades. The median tick frequency per instrument is 9.6×10^3 messages per session, with a 95th percentile burst rate of 1080 messages/sec.

The full maritime dataset comprises roughly 3.8×10^7 timestamped position reports collected from 500 distinct vessels operating in the Saronic Gulf (23.1–25.4°E, 37.1–38.4°N). Each record supplies a UTC time field, a vessel identifier, geodetic coordinates (longitude, latitude) and kinematic attributes in-

²<https://docs.oracle.com/en/java/javase/19/jmx/java-management-extensions-jmx-user-guide.html>

cluding heading, course over ground (COG), speed over ground (SOG), ship type code and the destination of the vessel. The stream averages 7.4×10^4 updates per ship, peaking above 1000 messages/sec, with vessel speeds spanning 0–38.6 kn (mean 1.9 kn, rising to 5.6 kn when vessels staying idle at ports are excluded). Passenger ferries (AIS ship type code 60), tugs (AIS ship type code 37), fast ships (AIS ship type code 90), pleasure boats (AIS ship type code 80) and product tankers (AIS ship type code 52) dominate the received messages. The file is a direct export of raw NMEA 0183 AIS messages decoded by shore receivers. The counters and ranges reported above rely on a light cleaning pass that removes rare latitude, longitude outliers before statistical aggregation.

Synopses and Synopses Parameters: Since SaaMS ingests JSON formatted Kafka messages, a CSV to JSON converter is also provided in the SaaMS code repository [32]. In the synopses used in our experiments we maintain CountMin (denoted by CM - $\epsilon = 0.002$, $\delta = 0.99$), HyperLogLog (denoted by HLL - $RS D = 0.02$) and Discrete Fourier Transform (denoted by DFT - $WindowSize = 500$, $SlideSize = 200$, $\#coefficients = 8$). We set these parameters after discussions with domain experts who share the datasets in the above cited links. As shown in Table 2, each synopsis is destined to support different types of analytics related to frequency estimation, distinct count and correlation, respectively, on the $\langle price, volume \rangle$ and positional attributes of stocks and vessels for the involved domain data streams.

Competitor Approaches: In Section 6.4 we perform an experimental comparison between SaaMS and the prior state-of-the-art, SDEaaS approach [31, 30]. The code of SDEaaS is provided open source as well [33].

Note that our experiments concentrate on computational and communication performance figures. We do not provide results for the synopses accuracy, since SaaMS does not alter in any way the accuracy guarantees of synopses. Theoretic bounds and experimental results on the accuracy of each synopsis can be found in related works cited in Table 2.

In our experimental evaluation we first examine SaaMS performance with respect to the scalability type requirements motivated in Section 1. We present triplets of figures describing the horizontal, vertical and federated scalability at the cloud side, the network side and the continuum as a whole. Since we notice little deviations between the conclusions drawn from the stock and the maritime datasets, we initially focus on the stock data. Then, we provide a comparative study between the previous state-of-the-art, the SDEaaS approach [30], and SaaMS on the Maritime Dataset. Again analogous results can be extracted for the stock market data.

6.1. SaaMS Horizontal Scalability

Figure 9 plots the achieved throughput (vertical axes) while varying parallelism (horizontal axes), at the cloud side (Figure 9(a)), at the network side (Figure 9(b)) and across the cloud to edge continuum as a whole (Figure 9(c)).

As illustrated in Figure 9(a), at the cloud side, SaaMS exhibits horizontal scalability that is polynomial while increasing parallelism from 3 to 18, for all the types (CM, HLL, DFT) of

maintained synopses as well as cumulatively (red line in Figure 9(a)). This result, as noted on the vertical axis label, stands for processing 100 streams maintaining 3 synopses per stream (300 synopses in total). Polynomial scalability, where increasing parallelism leads to a polynomial increase in throughput, indicates that as SaaMS scales out (more instances and processing threads are devoted), the overall performance improves at a rate that is faster than linear. This means SaaMS makes efficient use of the additional resources that become available to it in order to handle its workload. In addition, the exhibited polynomial scalability provides flexibility in scaling SaaMS to accommodate growing workloads. As the demand for processing power increases, SaaMS can add more resources to the system to maintain performance levels without hitting a performance plateau too quickly. Overall, polynomial scalability is a desirable characteristic in distributed systems like SaaMS because it indicates that the system can efficiently utilize resources, handle increasing workloads, and maintain performance as it scales.

At the network side, plotted in Figure 9(b), we observe that in this case, because the computational resources of Raspberry Pis are more restricted, SaaMS scales almost linearly, while processing 20 streams maintaining 3 synopses per stream, i.e., 60 synopses in total. This holds both upon examining individual CM, HLL, DFT synopses, as well as in cumulative throughput represented by the red line in Figure 9(b). More precisely, the red line in the figure has a sigmoid shape while increasing the number of Raspberry Pis in the network from 2 to 5. The blue line shows how throughput would be plotted in case of absolutely linear trend while increasing parallelism. For fewer than 4 Raspberry Pis, SaaMS is below linear throughput, while for 4 and 5 Raspberry Pis, the throughput of SaaMS shows a trend that is better than linear. Nevertheless, the blue shaded areas above and below the red line are almost equivalent in surface. Therefore, in total, SaaMS exhibits a linear trend in throughput increase upon adding more devices at the network side.

What is more important is that, across the cloud to edge continuum, Figure 9(c) shows that the overall performance of SaaMS is superior compared to examining the cloud (Figure 9(a)) or the network (Figure 9(b)) sides, separately. This holds both for individual types of synopses (black lines), and cumulatively (red line). In particular, in Figure 9(c) the number of parallel instances in the horizontal axis is varied between 6 to 23. These numbers are the sum of the parallelism at the cloud side and the number of Raspberry Pis used at the network side. We begin with a parallelism of 6 at the cloud side, we scale out to $6+2=8$ by adding 2 Raspberry Pis. Then, we switch to a setup with a parallelism of 9 at the cloud side and 3 Raspberry Pis at the network side ($9 + 3 = 12$ parallel instances) and to $12+4=16$. Finally, the last value of 23 in the horizontal axis is formed by a parallelism of 18 at the cloud side and 5 Raspberry Pis at the network side. In Figure 9(c), it can be observed that for fewer Raspberry Pis (2-3), where the throughput trend at the network side is below linear (Figure 9(b)), this slight under-performance is balanced out by the cloud side. On the other hand, for parallelism between 12 to 18, the cloud side shows a more moderate increase in throughput (Figure 9(a)). But being combined with the performance of the network side, which is above linear for

Figure 9: SaaS Horizontal Scalability

more than 3 Raspberry Pis, contributes in improving the overall throughput across the cloud to edge continuum. Therefore, both the black and the red lines in Figure 9(c) show a higher increasing trend in throughput compared to examining the network or the cloud side, separately.

6.2. SaaS Vertical Scalability

Figure 10 plots the vertical scalability of SaaS. Recall that vertical scalability refers to the ability to scale the computation with the number of processed streams. At the cloud side (Figure 10(a)) we fix parallelism to 9 and we explore the ability of SaaS to scale by progressively increasing the number of processed streams from 30 to 230 for each type of synopsis (CM, HLL, DFT). At the network side (Figure 10(b)) we use 3 Raspberry Pis and we explore the ability of SaaS to scale by progressively increasing the number of processed streams from 10 to 30 for each type of synopsis, due to the more resource constrained setup. Across the cloud to edge continuum (Figure 10(c)), to keep the correspondence between the graphs, we start by maintaining synopses for 40 streams, 30 streams from the cloud plot of Figure 10(a), plus 10 from the network side of Figure 10(b) (40 streams in total). Then, we change the setup to 60+20 streams, switching to 150+30 streams. Finally, to the 180 streams of the previous step, we start maintaining synopses for 80 more streams. This explains the horizontal axes among the various subfigures of Figure 10. In addition, note that by adding more streams we simultaneously increase the volume and velocity of the ingested data.

Figure 10(a) illustrates that, at the cloud side, SaaS scales linearly with increasing number of processed streams, both per synopsis type (black lines) and cumulatively (red line). This is an important result since even maintaining steady throughput with the number of processed streams would be satisfactory from a vertical scalability viewpoint. On the contrary, at the network side (Figure 10(b)), individual synopses maintain relatively steady throughput with increasing number of streams. Nonetheless, the cumulative throughput expressed by the red line in Figure 10(b) shows almost linear scaling. The reason for this behavior is that individual types of maintained synopses are not of absolutely steady throughput, but have a slightly increasing trend. Therefore, when the total throughput is computed, the small throughput increments per synopsis type accumulate

to an overall linear scaling trend with increasing number of processed streams. Finally, the vertical scalability across the continuum is dominated by the linear throughput increase at the cloud side (Figure 10(c)).

6.3. SaaS Federated Scalability

To judge the federated scalability of SaaS, we measure the amount of data communicated between microservice instances both at the cloud and at the network side, among Raspberry Pis. In Figure 11, the horizontal axes hold the number of parallel microservice instances, while there are 2 vertical axes in each graph. The leftmost vertical axes, in each of Figure 11(a), Figure 11(b) and Figure 11(c) measures the amount of communicated data between parallel microservice instances while maintaining the synopses as described for Figures 9(a), Figure 9(b) and Figure 9(c), correspondingly. Because simply mentioning the amount of data communicated by SaaS is not informative enough by itself, we also include the corresponding communication cost for answering continuous queries (see Output Estimation column in Table 2) in case we communicate the original streams instead of synopses. Therefore, all subfigures in Figure 11 have separate clusters of bars for the communication cost of answering queries using synopses, denoted by CM+HLL+DFT, versus the bars exposing the communication cost for answering queries using the original streams, termed NoCM+NoHLL+NoDFT. Given these, the rightmost vertical axis in each subfigure shows the communication ratio of Raw Streams over SaaS and the red line plots this ratio for the corresponding number of parallel microservice instances.

As shown by the red line in Figure 11, the federated scalability virtues of SaaS are more pronounced at the network (Figure 11(b)), rather than the cloud side (Figure 11(a)). In particular, at the cloud side, synopses can reduce the communication cost from an order of magnitude and up to 28 times compared to the naive approach of continuously communicating the raw streams in order to answer frequency estimation (for CM), distinct count (for HLL) and correlation (for DFT) queries. For the network side (Figure 11(b)), the communication cost reduction is between 170 and up to 188 times while varying the number of Raspberry Pis in the network, from 2 to 5. The overall communication cost reduction across the continuum (Figure 11(c)), therefore, is between 188 and 215 times.

(a) Vertical Scalability @ the Cloud Side

(b) Vertical Scalability @ the Network Side

(c) Vertical Scalability across the Continuum

Figure 10: SaaS Vertical Scalability

(a) Federated Scalability @ the Cloud Side

(b) Federated Scalability @ the Network Side

(c) Federated Scalability across the Continuum

Figure 11: SaaS Federated Scalability

The communication cost reduction ratio achieved by SaaS at the network side is much higher compared to the one at the cloud side. This is due to the data shuffling optimization performed by Kafka, according to the discussion in Section 5.2. Data shuffling optimization is possible at the cloud side of the network where the actual Kafka topics are handled, rather than at the network devices. Therefore, because SaaS communicates compact data summaries instead of the original raw streams even at the network side, its benefits are greater. This is an important argument exhibiting that simply deploying Kafka Streams across the cloud to edge continuum and merely relying on Kafka Streams optimization for federated scalability is not sufficient by itself. It is the streams synopses microservices of SaaS that enable federated scalability.

Moreover, we note that the communication cost reduction achieved by SaaS is expected to be even greater for larger networks. This is because, in larger network settings, the number of hops data need to travel in order to reach the query source has an aggregative effect in the total communication burden across the continuum.

6.4. SaaS vs SDEaaS

In this section we provide a comparative study on the current state of the art, the SDEaaS approach [31, 30] versus SaaS. SDEaaS has been proven [31, 30, 42] to outperform other (non-SDEaaS competitors) on the same datasets we use in this work. We use the Maritime dataset for this experiment, keeping synopses for up to 500 vessels.

SDEaaS is designed to operate at the cloud side and, therefore, we also restrict SaaS to deploying it only at the cloud

side. As discussed in Section 1, Section 2, Section 5.1 and Section 5.3, the microservice architecture of SaaS exploits Kafka and Kafka Streams in order to re-scale with zero downtime. SDEaaS on the other hand, as a Flink job, in each re-scaling decision requires to (i) take a savepoint, (ii) stop the running SDEaaS job, (iii) restart the job with altered parallelism, loading the previously taken savepoint. Therefore, for SDEaaS we measure two versions of its throughput. ‘‘SDEaaS only Uptime’’ measures throughput while the job is up and running, while ‘‘SDEaaS Uptime + Downtime’’ measures the average throughput throughout the job’s lifespan, also accounting for the fact that during downtimes, the throughput of SDEaaS is zeroed out.

In Figure 12, we have the vertical axis, which measures throughput, and two horizontal axes. The horizontal axis at the bottom shows the number of vessels for which we keep synopses (equivalent to those of the previous sections). Note that this entails both increasing the number of processed streams (vertical scalability) and the volume, velocity of the incoming streams (horizontal scalability). As the horizontal axis at the bottom shows, we begin with keeping synopses for 10 streams and we increase the number of streams up to 500. The more streams SaaS processes, the higher the volume and the velocity of ingested streams/vessels. The horizontal axis at the top of Figure 12 shows the parallelism and how it is altered during the experiment. So, all the candidate approaches begin with a parallelism of 3, when 50 streams are processed the parallelism switches to 6, it further increases at 100 streams to a value of 9 and reaches 12 for ~180 streams/vessels. Parallelism remains

Figure 12: SaaMS vs SDEaaS Comparison. The “SDEaaS only Uptime” line plots throughput without considering downtime due to re-scaling. “SDEaaS Uptime + Downtime” also accounts for zero throughput during re-scaling intervals.

fixed to 12 for the rest (180 - 500 streams/vessels) of the experiment. Note that we decide the timepoint for re-scaling based on the number of processed streams, as detailed above. Any mechanism that performs adaptive re-scaling in a different way is orthogonal to SaaMS. Proposing an autoscaler for SaaMS or SDEaaS is out of the scope of the current work and, therefore, we leave further investigation of this issue as future work.

As Figure 12 demonstrates, “SDEaaS only Uptime” can achieve between 1.5 to 3.8 times higher throughput compared to SaaMS for up to 200 streams. For more than 200 streams, SaaMS shows up to 1.5 times higher throughput. The reason for this behavior is that, SDEaaS ingests data from Kafka topics. Flink (and therefore SDEaaS) does not enforce strict collocation of Kafka topics with Flink tasks by default, as Kafka does. Therefore, when the ingestion (message consumption) load increases, the time devoted to reading messages from topics that are not necessarily collocated with the processing tasks, causes a drop in the overall throughput. On the contrary, as discussed in Section 5.2, Kafka by default performs data shuffling optimization.

Nevertheless, “SDEaaS only Uptime” shows an ideal picture about the performance of SDEaaS. This is because “SDEaaS only Uptime” totally ignores the intervals of downtime throughout the SDEaaS lifespan. While switching parallelism from $3 \rightarrow 6 \rightarrow 9 \rightarrow 12$ SDEaaS exhibits downtime the duration of which varies from tens of seconds to minutes depending on the state size of the respective savepoints. During these time intervals, no streaming tuples are processed and therefore SDEaaS’s throughput is zero.

When we take this into account, the true average throughput of SDEaaS as plotted by “SDEaaS Uptime + Downtime” is significantly deteriorated. For any number of streams/vessels above 40, SaaMS shows from 1.2 to 3 times higher throughput compared to SDEaaS. An important observation involves the greater deterioration in average throughput between “SDEaaS Uptime + DownTime” and “SDEaaS only Uptime”, SaaMS for larger number of vessels/streams. This behavior appears due to

the increased state size and the increased complexity of state organization as a result of maintaining more synopses for more streams. Therefore, it takes more time in Flink to take a savepoint of a larger state, stop the job and then load that larger state in order to restart the job under a different parallelism.

Finally, all 3 approaches show a considerable deterioration in throughput for any value streams/vessels above 300 due to the respective increase in the workload that progressively causes backpressures. Even in these cases, SaaMS provides 1.3 and up to 3 times higher throughput than SDEaaS.

7. Conclusion and Future Work

In this work we presented SaaMS, the first engine for maintaining hundreds of stream synopses of various types across the cloud to edge continuum. SaaMS attributes horizontal, vertical and federated scalability to the applications that utilize its synopses. It also ensures adaptivity to changing network conditions and stream statistical properties, with zero downtime. SaaMS outperforms the current state of the art by ensuring up to 3 times higher throughput, for hundreds of streams, according to our experimental evaluation. Our future work concentrates on deploying SaaMS in larger, real networks composed of devices with heterogeneous resource capacities. We are further developing a, Bayesian Optimization-based, optimization module for automatically setting and adapting the parallelism of each synopsis microservice, based on our prior experience [49].

Acknowledgments

Nikos Giatrakos was supported by the EU project CREX-DATA under Horizon Europe agreement No. 101092749.

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